

UNIVERSITY
OF
PADUA

Policy Brief

How to support parents in transmitting environmental responsibilities to children: Taking into account Humanist perspectives and values in the UK

-

RE-Green - Re-Greening Parental Responsibilities: An International Research Study on Humanist Parents' Pro-Environmental Activism

Intergenerational transmission of environmental values

The growing environmental issues necessitate a comprehensive approach to understanding the contexts, needs, and values of families from diverse belief systems to foster a collaborative effort among the families, local communities, governmental bodies, and global institutions. This policy brief addresses the necessity of recognising the perspectives of parents of various beliefs on raising environmentally conscious children, exploring their challenges, insights, and experiences across the domains of family, school, community, and society in the UK. It particularly focuses on Humanist, atheist and agnostic parents, and the environmental outlook of Humanism, a non-religious worldview that places the welfare and happiness of human beings and other sentient life at the centre of ethical decision-making, on the basis of reason and humanity.

Recognising perspectives from belief systems is essential for crafting inclusive policies that support parents and educators in raising environmentally aware children. By creating a cohesive framework that promotes sustainable practices across all levels of society, this policy brief provides actionable recommendations to address these issues, ensuring a collaborative effort towards a sustainable present and future in the UK.

About RE-Green

This policy brief is based on the findings from the UK fieldwork of the research project “Re-Greening parental responsibilities: An international research study on Humanist parents’ pro-environmental activism” (RE-Green). RE-Green is funded by the Supporting TAlent in ReSearch at University of Padua Grant Programme-STARs (NextGenerationEU), hosted by University of Padua, Department of Philosophy, Sociology, Education and Applied Psychology (FISPPA) and led by Dr Morena Tartari. The project investigates the pro-environment activism of Humanist parents, grandparents and young people, and their work to socialise the next generation to green responsibilities in the UK and Italy. It aims to reframe the idea of environmental citizenship, investigating contemporary pro-environment activism of the Humanist Movement in the public and private sphere. The project offers policy briefs for each country involved, with this particular brief focusing on the UK context. For what concerns the UK context, in the research project were involved people who identified themselves as 'Humanist', terms which include atheist and agnostic people.

RE-Green employs various research approaches and methods. In the initial phase of the project, we analysed Humanist institutional discourses, particularly on how environment-human relationships are discursively constructed. In the second phase, we conducted interviews with Humanist parents, grandparents and young people to explore social aspects of how environmental and non-religious values are intergenerationally transmitted. In the final phase, we organised focus group sessions with Humanist experts, encompassing individuals with diverse roles in Humanism such as Humanist celebrants, school speakers, pastoral carers, chaplains, administrators, coordinators, chairs, as well as Humanist parents.

Highlights

1. Understanding environmental perspectives of families and values of Humanist parenting

Families from diverse belief systems have different approaches and set of values for parenting and environmental care. The Humanist approach to parenting emphasizes nurturing children who think for themselves, make decisions based on evidence and science and engage in reasoning, critical thinking and ethical action, and develop empathy for others. Through our interviews with Humanist parents, we discovered that they valued transmitting their children a sense of responsibility towards the planet and future generations. As identified in Humanist institutional discourses, Humanists believe they are part of nature as another animal, thus responsible for taking care of it. Transmission of environmental values and responsibilities is considered part of parental responsibilities from a Humanist perspective, that helps defining and improving the concept of green parental responsibility. Moreover, our focus group participants raised the importance of fostering awareness among young people and parents about the contributions of diverse belief systems to environmental conservation and the nurturing of responsible individuals.

2. Considering school support for raising environmentally aware children

In considering support for parents for raising environmentally-aware children, help from schools appear critical. In the UK, certain schools participate in the Eco-Schools Project, engaging children in initiatives aimed at fostering sustainable practices within the school environment.

Humanists value encouraging children to volunteer and take action on environmental issues as a social responsibility. While finding these school initiatives helpful in sensitising children to environmental values, some Humanist participants expressed concerns that certain school practices posed a risk of greenwashing in the eyes of their children. The children would like to have a stronger say and voice in the school's environmentalist strategy. Furthermore, these initiatives are not yet extensively embraced across primary, secondary, further, and higher education institutions.

3. Building community strategies for environmental care

Involving parents and children in local environmental care initiatives is a powerful means of cultivating environmentally conscious communities. In the UK, some councils develop and implement specific environmental strategies for community living.

Alongside other belief groups, Humanists have their own environmental stance. Humanists believe in one life only, without an afterlife, and thus hold that we are all responsible for creating a world in which everyone, including future generations, has the opportunity to live life to the full in the here and now. They find and promote happiness, fulfilment, and joy in connecting with and appreciating the natural world, as stated in interviews and focus group sessions with Humanist experts and parents based in the UK.

4. Towards developing an environmental citizenship

"Environmental Citizenship" encompasses responsible pro-environmental behaviour at local, national, and global levels. It involves individual and collective actions to address environmental challenges, achieve sustainability, and nurture a healthy relationship with nature, including exercise of environmental rights and duties, identification of structural causes of issues, and engagement in civic participation for environmental justice, as defined by [the European Network for Environmental Citizenship – ENEC \(2018\)](#).

Humanists advocate for a collective responsibility toward the environment, our communities, societies, and the planet as a whole. As affirmed in Humanist institutional discourses, Humanism promotes thinking for yourself and acting for everyone. When addressing life's challenges, including environmental issues, Humanism relies on scientific principles. Developing an environmental citizenship is a comprehensive way of acting together in different ways that the beliefs of citizens as well as cultures offer.

Recommendations

1. Promoting belief literacy and green parental responsibilities

Policymakers and relevant services should consider promoting belief literacy, particularly among young people and parents, to foster a more inclusive environmental stance and encourage collaborative efforts. Belief systems can offer a set of values for living responsibly and Humanism, as a non-religious belief system, advocates for evidence-based environmental actions and ethical, sustainable living practices. Humanists are guided by reason and science and recognise a moral duty towards the welfare of fellow beings, other sentient life and the natural world. Humanist parents value parental responsibilities in guiding children to engage with nature and to look after the planet. Green parental responsibilities, as novel conceptualisation, can help understanding the work of parents in transmitting environmental values to the next generation, nurturing children's relationship with nature and the planet Earth, and sensitising them to environmental responsibilities. Initiatives to support parents with diverse religious and non-religious beliefs should also take into considerations the Humanist standpoint of environmental conservation and parental responsibilities.

2. Strengthening the ecological practices of schools

Opportunities for children and young people to lead the way should be provided within the eco-schooling contexts. Initiatives such as Green Flag accreditation frameworks should emphasise tangible outcomes rooted in scientific principles to mitigate the risk of greenwashing, with active support from school administrators. These initiatives should be promoted for adoption across all levels of education, from primary to higher education institutions, ensuring a consistent approach to environmental education and action.

Rationality and scientific thinking are central to the Humanist approach. Humanists advocate for the inclusion of a Humanist approach in environmental education and across different curriculum areas.

3. Building environmentally together communities

Each council should develop a transparent and accountable environmental strategy, ensuring its effective implementation. These strategies should take into account the various ways in which belief communities contribute to environmental care. Humanist communities should be represented in environmental projects.

Councils and relevant decision-makers should encourage intergenerational participation in environmental campaigns and practices. This provides a valuable opportunity for young people to learn environmental values from their family members and community through practical engagement rather than mere instruction.

4. Reframing environmental actions and citizenship

Initiatives for encouraging communities should aim not just at avoiding harm to or destruction of the environment, but at active citizenship in which human beings work together to improve their world. Responsibility is central to Humanist thinking, and Humanists advocate initiatives fostering the recognition that human beings all belong to a wider community which encompasses future generations and the natural world which we share with other living things.

These initiatives should move away from traditional environmentalism and instead offer effective ways of dealing with uncertainties of climate change, and to help young people to cope with the stresses and anxieties of what they may see as a frightening future by working together to meet the challenge.

UNIVERSITY
OF
PADUA

Funded by the
European Union
NextGenerationEU

Authors

Dr Hamide Elif Üzümcü

Postdoctoral Research Fellow in RE-Green
Department of Philosophy, Sociology,
Education and Applied Psychology (FISPPA),
University of Padua, Padova, Italy
hamideelif.uzumcu@unipd.it

Dr Morena Tartari

Principal Investigator of RE-Green
Department of Sociology and Social Work,
Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania
morena.tartari@ubbcluj.ro

RE-Green is funded by the Supporting TALENT in
ReSEARCH at University of Padua - STARS Grant
Programme.

RE-Green | [Facebook](#)

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.12779384](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12779384)